

Three conjectures

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First conjecture. For at least one mathematical theory it is possible to find a formula, which, depending on the result, is able to establish whether a mathematical statement is true, false or unprovable.

Second conjecture. The complexity of this formula is directly proportional to the complexity of the mathematical theory for which it is formulated.

Third conjecture. It is possible to determine how complex a certain area of mathematics is compared to another.